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Research Article

IMPORTANCE OF ORAL ANTIBIOTICS “CIPROFLOXACIN VS NEOMYCIN” FOR SECONDARY PROPHYLAXIS OF PORTO- SYSTEMIC ENCEPHALOPATHY IN PATIENTS OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS

Dr. Umama Najam¹, Dr. Pervez Rashid Birmani², Dr. Shazia Munawar³

¹ Rawal Institute of Health Sciences, Islamabad

² Central Park Medical College, Lahore

³ DHQ Hospital, Jehlum

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Abstract:

Objective: Liver cirrhosis is one of the major causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide but the exact frequency of liver cirrhosis is unknown. The incidence of hepatic encephalopathy (HE), also called s porto- systemic encephalopathy (PSE), is 24% in patients with cirrhosis.

Aim: To compare the efficacy of neomycin and ciprofloxacin for secondary prophylaxis of secondary porto-systemic encephalopathy (PSE) in patients with liver cirrhosis.

Place and duration: In the Medicine department of Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi for six months duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Study design: Randomized Control Trail.

Method: 280 cases were randomly divided into two groups. Patients coming with PSE were included after they became conscious. Ciprofloxacin was given to one group and neomycin was given to the other group after discharge. Patients were observed for recurrence of PSE for 6 months.

Results: Among 280 patients, the average age of patients in the neomycin group was 50.35 ± 6.72 , and as in the ciprofloxacin group - 50.33 ± 7.09 . A total of 59.6% of patients were male and 40.4% of patients were female. 1.07% of patients with grade I hepatic encephalopathy, 37.14% with grade II, 39.28% with grade III, 22.5% of patients with grade IV hepatic encephalopathy. After 3 months, in the neomycin group, 46.32% of patients did not develop systemic encephalopathy, 13.23% of patients developed systemic encephalopathy, 26.47% of patients died. , 69% of patients developed systemic encephalopathy, 31.94% of patients expired, 9.94% of patients lost observation. Pearson chi-sq. = 66.619 P = 0.000. During a 6-month follow-up in the neomycin group, 46.32% of patients did not develop port systemic encephalopathy, 13.23% of patients developed port-systemic encephalopathy, 26.47% of patients died. In the ciprofloxacin-treated group, 10.41% of patients did not develop systemic encephalopathy in the port system, 50.69% of patients developed in the port system encephalopathy, 31.94% died.

Conclusion: Neomycin is more effective than ciprofloxacin in the prevention of systemic encephalopathy. Mortality in the neomycin group is lower than in the ciprofloxacin group.

Key words: liver cirrhosis, PSE, secondary prevention.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Umama Najam,

Rawal Institute of Health Sciences, Islamabad

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis is one of the major causes of morbidity and mortality in the world, but the exact occurrence of liver cirrhosis is unknown. Estimates show that up to 1% of the population affects the whole world, but this rate is even higher in most developing countries in Asia and Africa, where chronic hepatitis B and C are more common¹⁻³. Cirrhosis is becoming an epidemic in Pakistan due to the high incidence of hepatitis B and C in our community. Unfortunately, the prognosis for patients with liver cirrhosis is poor. An annual mortality rate of 50-70 percent was observed. This is often due to the advanced stage of liver cirrhosis, leading to catastrophic complications⁹. Fibrosis is a key event that leads to liver cirrhosis and life-threatening complications⁴⁻⁶. Cirrhosis and its complications affect general socioeconomic values. One of the major complications of liver cirrhosis is hepatic encephalopathy (HE). The incidence of HE, also called portosystemic encephalopathy (PSE) in patients with cirrhosis, is 24%. While neuromuscular symptoms can sometimes be studied, they are characterized by neuropsychiatric expression, which can vary significantly from mild mental change to coma⁷. An important consequence of the disease is that portal blood circulation persists in the systemic circulation through port collateral vessels, thereby preventing liver metabolism. Further research in recent years has made significant progress in preventing and treating common complications of liver cirrhosis. HE is often caused by identifiable factors such as varicose bleeding, intestinal infections, constipation, and electrolyte imbalance. Proper identification and treatment of triggers is the key to preventing liver cirrhosis complications. The use of lactose and antibiotics plays an important role in changing the intestinal flora, and thus in preventing H E. By using effective oral antibiotics to prevent the recurrence of PSE, we can reduce the incidence and mortality of liver cirrhosis, thereby reducing the socioeconomic burden associated with this disease. In antibiotics, it is widely used in the prevention of neomycin. Its use is limited to topical or oral preparations due to the toxicity of neomycin⁷⁻⁹. The benefits of neomycin, the most commonly used drug, are associated with effects on bacteria in the colon. Although the oral absorption of neomycin in the stomach and intestines is on average just 0.58%. Plasma neomycin levels are negligible. It should not be used for more than six months and beware renal issues and hearing poisoning. Although ciprofloxacin is rationally used in clinical practice, evidence of the usefulness of these drugs in secondary prevention is

far from obvious. A large randomized trial is needed to determine the role of ciprofloxacin in the prevention of PSE. In our country, the treatment of these patients is not only difficult, but also complex, because these patients appear at a very late stage. Several treatment options are available. Neomycin and ciprofloxacin are inexpensive to treat these patients and can easily be found in our environment. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of these two drugs to establish guidelines for the treatment of patients who prevent complications in patients with porto-systemic hepatic encephalopathy, and patients will benefit from these treatment options.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This randomized longitudinal trial was conducted at the Medicine department of Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi for six months duration from March 2019 to March 2020. There are 280 cases calculated using the Raosoft calculator described by Ezechi et al. The margin of error was 5% and the confidence level was 95%. Consecutive patients of PSE were randomized in ciprofloxacin and neomycin group.

Inclusion Criteria:

All those patients between the age of between 18-60 years with liver cirrhosis established and those patients recovered from current episode of Porto systemic Encephalopathy in hospital and being discharged were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with a history of mental or sedative diseases.
- Patients with portal vein thrombosis during ultrasound.
- History of alcohol consumption.
- Awareness change due to drug intoxication
- Hypersensitivity to neomycin or ciprofloxacin.
- Patients with underlying conditions such as glomerulonephritis, renal failure and congestive heart failure.
- Patients who are already taking oral antibiotics regularly.
- Patients with contraindications to the use of aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones.

Clinic visits took place on days 7, 14, 56 and 112 followed by 168 days (end of treatment period). Patients were also monitored for weeks without clinical visits for any adverse drug reactions or PSE attacks, and SPSS 16.0 was used for statistical analysis. Qualitative and quantitative data were used in the chi-square test to assess the significance between two groups other than interference, and was statistically significant at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Hematological parameters, BUN and prothrombin time of both groups do not show a significant difference after inclusion of the studied patients ($P > 0.05$). The mean age of patients in the neomycin group was 50.35 ± 6.72 and 50.33 ± 7.09 in the ciprofloxacin group. ($P = 0.981$) (Table 1) 59.6% of patients were male and 40.4% female. In the neomycin group, 56.6% were male and 43.4% female. In the ciprofloxacin group, 62.5% were men and 37.7% were women. Pearson Square = 1.005 $P = 0.316$. In the neomycin group, 26.47% of patients expired and 13.67% of patients had control loss. In the ciprofloxacin group, 31.94% of patients expired and 9.94% of patients disappeared. These patients were excluded from the final analysis model. During the three-month follow-up period, 27.85% of patients did not develop systemic encephalopathy, while 32.26% of patients developed systemic

encephalopathy, 29.28% of patients died and lost 10.35%. In the ciprofloxacin group (50.69%), a statistically significant number (Pearson chi-sq = 66.619 value $P = 0.000$) developed systemic encephalopathy compared to 13.23% of the neomycin group. In general, 27.85% of patients with an observation period of up to six months did not develop systemic encephalopathy, 32.26% of patients developed port encephalopathy, 29.28% of patients died and were removed again from the final analysis. In the neomycin group, 46.32% of patients did not develop in port systemic encephalopathy, 13.23% of patients developed in port encephalopathy, 26.47% of patients died. In the ciprofloxacin group, 10.41% of patients did not develop systemic encephalopathy, 50.69% of patients developed systemic encephalopathy, and 31.94% of patients discontinued treatment. = 63.138 $P = 0.000$.

Table 1: Comparison of two group's laboratory values

Characteristics	Neomycin	Ciprofloxacin	P-value
Haemoglobin level (g/dl)	8.98± 1.9	9.18±2.02	0.390
Total leukocyte count×10 ³ /mm ³	10.0 ± 16.9	9.88±9.23	0.935
Platelet count×10 ³ /mm ³	105.29±76.9	151.88±53.3	0.314
Serum bilirubin(mg/dl)	1.87±1.86	1.68±1.35	0.328
Serum albumin(g/dl)	3.19±0.55	3.18±0.7	0.957
Serum creatinine(mg/dl)	1.23±0.44	1.36±0.59	0.041
Blood urea nitrogen(mg/dl)	34.34±16.6 1	36.33±16.61	0.318
Prothrombin time(seconds)	2.63±0.7	2.50±0.78	0.135

Table 2 Comparison of TP score and follow up days

	Treatment group	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
CTP class score	Neomycin	11.47059	5.524278	0.271
	Ciprofloxacin	10.93056	1.945599	
Days of Follow up	Neomycin	106.9118	64.95018	0.000
	Ciprofloxacin	47.6111	48.09884	

Table-3: Sign and Symptoms among treatment group

Sign and Symptoms	Treatment group of patients		
	Neomycin	Ciprofloxacin	Total
Pusle>100/min	11.76%	14.58%	13.21%
BP< 90 systolic	0.73%	1.38%	1.07%
Ascites	84.55%	87.5%	86.07%
Spiderangioma	11.02%	13.19%	12.14%
Ankle edema	77.94%	74.30%	76.07%
Malena	83.82%	77.77%	80.71%
GI Bleeding	64.70%	63.88%	64.28%
Splenomegaly	98.52%	95.13%	96.7%
Dilated portal vein	4.41%	4.86%	4.64%

Table 4: Grades of Hepatic Encephalopathy:

Grade of Hepatic encephalopathy	Treatment group of patient		Total
	Neomycin	Ciprofloxacin	
Grade I	0.73	1.38	1.07
Grade II	37.5	36.80	37.14
Grade III	40.44	38.19	39.28
Grade IV	21.32	23.61	33.5

Chi- square= 0.540 p-value=0.910

Grade 1- Trivial lack of awareness, shortened attention span. Impairment noted on arithmetical testing **Grade**

2- Lethargy, disorientation in time, clear personality change, or inappropriate behavior

Grade 3- Very drowsy, semi-comatose but responsive to stimuli, confused, gross disorientation in time or space, bizarre behavior

Grade 4- Coma

DISCUSSION:

Prevention of open hepatic encephalopathy is an important goal in the treatment of patients with cirrhosis, especially if the recurrent symptoms of encephalopathy are devastating and lead to poor nutrition and incompatibility by reducing self-care which repeatedly leads to serious symptoms, repeated hospitalizations and poor quality of life. There has been no significant progress in H E therapy in recent years⁸⁻¹⁰. The most relevant are encouraging results on the benefit against the risk of using antibiotics. Oral antibiotics close to their low absorption can reduce small cell intestinal hypertrophy (SIBO), which is often associated with liver cirrhosis. Therefore, antibiotics may be primarily useful in emergency situations to control ammonia production, but direct comparisons in the treatment of HD are insufficient. This study found that neomycin reduced the risk of hepatic encephalopathy attacks within 6 months in patients with a new history of recurrent hepatic encephalopathy¹¹⁻¹². The effectiveness of specific neomycin sulfate treatment has not yet been experimentally studied. Strauss et al. For five years, 102 patients with cirrhosis developed hepatic encephalopathy on admission or during hospitalization, and 39 were randomly assigned to treatment with neomycin sulfate or placebo. The disqualified group of patients (n = 63) was compared with the randomized group (n = 39) and there was no statistical difference in Child-Pugh classification, etiology of cirrhosis, causative agents and grade of hepatic encephalopathy¹¹⁻¹². A remedy for liver encephalopathy was the control of precipitants associated with "per os" or 6 g of neomycin sulfate with placebo. The time between the beginning of the therapeutic procedure and the decrease in hepatic encephalopathy to zero was 39.11 ± 23.04 hours for the neomycin active group and 49.47 ± 21.92 hours

for the placebo group, but this difference was not statistically significant¹³⁻¹⁴.

In one study, colorectal microflora changes were studied in 14 patients treated orally with ciprofloxacin. All patients were affected by hepatic encephalopathy. In the first days a significant decrease in the number of enterobacteria was observed at both doses; 3-6 treatments. It disappears completely from its days and returns to normal within 2 weeks after the end of treatment. Gram-positive and gram-negative aerobic and anaerobic flora have not changed significantly. As a result of these results, the treatment of six patients with PSE (Grade 2-3) was investigated by examining changes in colorectal microflora, the presence of circulating endotoxins and blood levels of ammonium before, during and after. 12-day therapy¹³. Significant reduction or inhibition of enterobacteria and immediate normalization of blood ammonium levels, disappearance of circulating endotoxins and clear clinical improvement were observed in 5 (83%) 6 patients. The limitations of this study are that it is not a blind study and it does not assess health-related quality of life. Antibiotic treatment of both groups was performed using a random longitudinal study, so no blind study was possible. However, the low dose of neomycin and ciprofloxacin were well tolerated by all patients and none of the patients dropped out due to side effects. This study is unique compared to other studies on secondary prevention of porto-systemic encephalopathy because the minimum dose of neomycin 500 mg OD compared to the 6-month booster dose of 750 mg ciprofloxacin weekly with such a large sample of ciprofloxacin¹⁵. Treatment with neomycin reduced the risk of hospitalization for portosystemic encephalopathy, reflecting the clinical relevance of our study. Our study showed that "neomycin" was associated with episodes of

open portosystemic encephalopathy compared to "ciprofloxacin". The incidence of adverse events in general and adverse events associated with infection is similar in the "neomycin" group and the "ciprofloxacin" group. In summary, this study showed a strong protective effect of "neomycin" against attacks of systemic encephalopathy compared to ciprofloxacin.

CONCLUSION:

This study suggests that neomycin is more effective than ciprofloxacin in preventing Porto systemic encephalopathy.

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